

1 Water as a decisive factor in the thermal transformation of cellulose 2 into activated carbon

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13 Abstract

14 One-step KOH activation enables the direct conversion of cellulose-based biomass into
15 activated carbon (AC), yet reproducible control over pore structure and carbon yield remains
16 challenging. While many studies emphasize the KOH-to-precursor mass ratio, the water
17 volume used for dissolving a fixed amount of KOH is rarely regarded as an independent
18 parameter. Here, we demonstrate that the amount of water introduced with the KOH solution
19 and its spatial distribution within the cellulose precursor after impregnation (bulk-absorbed vs
20 surface-associated) govern the thermal transformation pathway and the resulting AC
21 properties. Using paper sheets with a defined absorption capacity as a model precursor, ACs
22 were prepared at constant KOH loading (1:1) while systematically varying the added water
23 volume. This approach establishes distinct initial conditions, ranging from complete solution
24 uptake to excess external solution. Combined thermal analysis (TGA-MS), ATR-FTIR, XRD,

25 XPS, electron microscopy, N₂ adsorption, and SAXS reveal that exceeding the precursor's
26 absorption capacity promotes early carbonate formation, enhances alkaline hydrolysis, delays
27 char formation, reduces carbon yield, and strengthens CO₂-assisted physical activation,
28 leading to larger pores. In contrast, reduced water addition shifts the pathway toward earlier
29 charring, limits hydroxide conversion, increases yield, and promotes micropore-dominated
30 structures. These findings identify water volume at constant KOH loading as a decisive variable
31 in one-step activation and demonstrate that it must be controlled alongside mass ratio to
32 achieve reproducible, application-tailored ACs from biomass.

33 *Keywords: Activated carbon, Cellulose, One-step KOH activation, KOH solution impregnation,*
34 *Water volume, Pore structure control*

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Activated carbon (AC) is a porous, electrically conductive carbon material and its application-
37 relevant properties are largely governed by pore architecture and surface chemistry [1-4]. Due
38 to its high internal surface area, tunable porosity, and chemical stability, AC has been
39 extensively studied for electrochemical energy storage (e.g., supercapacitors and battery
40 electrodes) [5-8], gas adsorption/storage (e.g., CO₂ capture, H₂ storage) [3, 9-12] and water
41 treatment (removal of dyes, pharmaceuticals, and heavy metals) [4, 13-15]. For
42 supercapacitors, pore size distribution must balance charge storage and ion transport.
43 Ultramicropores (≤ 0.7 nm) and micropores (≤ 2 nm) provide most of the surface area for charge
44 storage. However, purely microporous networks often suffer from transport limitations at high
45 charge rates. Introducing mesopores (2-50 nm) and macropores (>50 nm) can reduce diffusion
46 limitations and electrolyte resistance [16-19]. Consequently, the ability to engineer a targeted
47 hierarchy of micro-/mesoporosity is central to AC design for fast-charging devices. For gas
48 storage and separation, the "optimal" porosity shifts toward smaller pores. In physisorption-
49 based hydrogen storage, ultramicropores dominate uptake at low pressure [20-22]. These
50 examples demonstrate that high surface area alone is not a sufficient design criterion, rather,
51 AC synthesis must be controllable enough to deliver application-specific pore size distributions.

52 Activation methods are typically classified as physical (e.g. CO₂ and/or steam gasification) [23-
53 26], chemical (impregnation with activating agents such as KOH, K₂CO₃, NaOH, or phosphoric
54 acid followed by heat treatment) [2, 27-32], or a combination of both [33-35]. Among chemical
55 activators, KOH is widely used because it can generate high specific surface areas (SSA's)
56 ranging from 1000-4000 m²/g and large micropore volumes [2, 27, 28, 36, 37]. KOH activation
57 is described by a combination of (i) redox etching of carbon, (ii) gasification reactions involving
58 H₂O/CO/CO₂/H₂, and (iii) intercalation of elemental potassium into carbon lattices, which
59 expands carbon layers and contributes to micropore formation upon its removal [27, 36, 38,
60 39]

61 Producing AC from biomass and biowaste offers a route toward lower-cost sorbents and
62 electrodes while supporting circular economy concepts. Numerous precursors, including
63 organic waste materials such as nut shells, sawdust, spent coffee grounds or brewer's spent
64 grain have been converted into ACs for water purification and energy-related applications [3,
65 40-42]. However, biomass-derived ACs often exhibit batch-to-batch variability [43-45]. In real
66 feedstocks, precursor properties can shift with harvesting season, storage history, and
67 processing, which complicates the reproducible production of a defined pore structure [46-51].
68 The precursor microstructure governs the interaction with chemical activators such as KOH
69 and, consequently, the pore size distribution (PSD) and SSA of the AC. Limited accessibility
70 in more crystalline or dense regions leads to heterogeneous absorption of the KOH solution,
71 thereby affecting the intensity and uniformity of etching during activation [2].

72 In contrast to conventional two-step KOH activation, in which the biomass is first carbonized
73 into a hydrophobic char prior to solution impregnation, direct impregnation of the biomass
74 followed by conversion to AC in a single thermal treatment enables intimate KOH-precursor
75 contact at the molecular scale [38, 52]. This approach is particularly well suited to cellulosic
76 precursors, as cellulose contains abundant oxygen-containing functional groups and a
77 microfibrillar architecture that promote strong interactions with alkaline solutions and facilitate
78 efficient uptake of KOH [38, 52-56]. Numerous studies have focused on identifying activation

79 temperature, dwell time, and the KOH to precursor mass ratio that maximize SSA without
80 excessive burn-off [27, 48, 57-61]. Increasing these parameters typically enhances SSA and
81 pore volume up to an optimum, beyond which over-etching leads to pore widening and
82 collapse, reducing SSA and yield. However, even when these activation parameters are kept
83 constant, the water volume used for KOH dissolution can create different precursor states prior
84 to heat treatment.

85 This applied water volume is particularly relevant for KOH solution impregnation, which is
86 widely used for biomass precursors [9, 48, 62-64] alongside physical mixing with solid KOH
87 [27, 28, 65-68]. At constant KOH loading, the water volume used to dissolve KOH determines
88 whether the solution is fully absorbed by the precursor or remains as excess liquid, thereby
89 influencing the spatial distribution and effective uptake of KOH within the matrix. Consequently,
90 distinct initial precursor conditions are created for the early stages of pyrolysis, which can lead
91 to different thermal conversion pathways and AC structures. Non-uniform impregnation, for
92 example, can cause localized over-etching and pore collapse in KOH-rich regions during high-
93 temperature treatment, while KOH-poor regions remain under-activated [2]. The water volume
94 also influences drying kinetics and the time-temperature window in which KOH can undergo
95 side reactions before the onset of high-temperature activation. Literature reports show that
96 KOH can convert into less reactive potassium salts already at low temperatures during drying
97 in air [29, 69]. Even in an inert atmosphere, potassium-containing cellulose releases CO₂
98 during the initial stages of pyrolysis at temperatures below 300 °C [29, 70-72], which can further
99 consume hydroxide. Consequently, at fixed KOH mass, the water volume can determine how
100 much reactive hydroxide remains available in the activation-relevant temperature range and
101 how strongly it contributes to micropore formation.

102 This work examines how the solution volume, controlled by the amount of water added to a
103 constant KOH mass, modifies cellulose-to-AC conversion and consequently PSD, SSA, and
104 yield. To isolate this effect, paper sheets are used as a model precursor, while activation
105 temperature, dwell time, and the KOH-to-precursor mass ratio are kept constant at 1:1. Our

106 approach exploits the finite maximum uptake volume of aqueous KOH in paper sheets of
107 defined mass. The applied water volume therefore determines whether the solution is fully
108 absorbed by the sheet or whether an external liquid fraction persists as film or pooled solution
109 in the crucible. By systematically varying this parameter at constant KOH mass, the influence
110 of liquid volume can be directly isolated, revealing how it shapes pyrolytic conversion and
111 thereby governs porosity development and carbon yield. Elucidating this relationship enhances
112 reproducibility, enables targeted pore structure design and provides valuable input for scaling
113 up KOH-based biomass activation processes.

114 **2. Materials and methods**

115 *2.1. Materials*

116 Paper precursors were prepared from commercial unbeaten bleached hardwood pulp provided
117 by Lenzing (Lenzing, Austria). Activation was performed using KOH solutions of varying
118 concentrations prepared from KOH pellets ($\geq 85\%$, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), while 1 M
119 HCl (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) was employed for post-carbonization washing. All
120 chemicals were used as received.

121 *2.2. Preparation of ACs*

122 Precursor papers with a grammage of 160 g/m² were produced using a Rapid-Köthen sheet
123 former according to ISO 5269-2, cut into sheets of similar dimensions, and stored in a climate-
124 controlled room at 23 °C and 50% relative humidity (ISO 187).

125 The maximum uptake volume of aqueous KOH by the paper sheets was determined in
126 preliminary tests. In these, each sheet was weighed and a KOH solution containing a dry KOH
127 mass equal to the sheet mass (KOH:paper = 1:1, w/w) was prepared while increasing the
128 added water stepwise. After each step, the solution was applied and complete absorption
129 (uniform wetting with no external liquid) was assessed visually. The highest water addition still
130 yielding complete absorption corresponded to 35 w.% KOH. Subsequently, KOH solutions of

131 20, 25, 30, and 35 w.% were prepared. To maintain a constant KOH-to-paper mass ratio (1:1,
 132 w/w), the required volume for each sheet was calculated as

$$V_{KOH\ solution} = \frac{m_{sheet}}{w * \rho} \quad (1)$$

133 where $V_{KOH\ solution}$ is the applied solution volume, m_{sheet} is the sheet mass, w is the KOH mass
 134 fraction, and ρ is the solution density. Lower-concentration solutions therefore require larger
 135 volumes, thereby enabling systematic variation of the water content in the applied KOH
 136 solution across the sample series.

137 The sheets were impregnated in an Al_2O_3 crucible using a pipette and then directly transferred
 138 into a tube furnace (TZF 15/610, Carbolite, Neuhausen, Germany). In the tube furnace,
 139 specimens were dried at 120 °C for 1 h in a N_2 atmosphere (320 mL/min; heating rate 5°C/min),
 140 then heated to 750 °C and held at this temperature for 1 h. After the thermal treatment, the
 141 ACs were washed with 1 M HCl and distilled water to neutral pH and dried at 105 °C overnight
 142 before storage in sealed containers. To assess intermediate stages of thermal conversion, an
 143 additional set of samples was removed from the furnace upon reaching 250 °C, photographed,
 144 and subsequently analyzed by XRD and FTIR.

145 Table 1. Average KOH solution concentrations, corresponding volumes, and masses applied
 146 per precursor paper sheet for activation. The precursor-to-KOH mass ratio was kept constant
 147 at 1:1.

Specimens	Avg. KOH solution concentration [w.%]	Avg. KOH solution volume per sheet [mL]	Avg. dry KOH mass per sheet [g] / [mmol]
C20	20	1.53	0.37 / 6.59
C25	25	1.20	
C30	30	0.95	
C35	35	0.78	

148 * Exact values depend on the individual sheet mass, which varies by ± 0.004 g.

149 2.3. Characterization

150 *2.3.1 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) with / without coupled mass spectrometer (TGA-MS)*

151 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out on a Netzsch 449-F1 Jupiter instrument
152 (Netzsch, Selb, Germany) to study the thermal behavior of the KOH-impregnated precursors
153 (C20-C35). About 15-20 mg of specimen was placed in a ceramic crucible and heated from 30
154 to 750 °C at 5 °C min⁻¹ under a constant nitrogen flow. Isothermal steps of 1 h were applied at
155 120 °C and 750 °C to replicate the drying and activation stages in the tube furnace. For
156 specimens C20 and C35, additional TGA-MS measurements were performed using a Perkin
157 Elmer TGA 8000 (Perkin Elmer, Connecticut, USA) thermogravimetric analyzer under nitrogen
158 atmosphere. The temperature program was identical to that used for the TGA measurements
159 without MS coupling. Volatile decomposition products, including CO₂ and H₂O, were monitored
160 online using a Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010 SE single quadrupole mass spectrometer (Shimadzu
161 Europa GmbH, Duisburg, Germany).

162 *2.3.2 Attenuated total reflection Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR)*

163 ATR-FTIR spectra of the partially carbonized papers after 250 °C were recorded using an
164 Agilent Cary 630 spectrometer (Santa Clara, CA, USA) fitted with a diamond ATR accessory
165 and a spectral resolution of < 2 cm⁻¹. Measurements were carried out in the range of 4000-650
166 cm⁻¹, with 64 scans averaged per spectrum. Data processing and analysis were performed
167 with OriginPro 2020.

168 *2.3.3 X-ray diffraction (XRD)*

169 X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed using a STADI P diffractometer (STOE,
170 Darmstadt, Germany) operated in transmission geometry. Monochromatic Mo K α_1 radiation
171 with a wavelength of $\lambda = 0.70930 \text{ \AA}$ was employed as the X-ray source. The diffractograms
172 were recorded over a 2θ range from 4 ° to 55 °, using a step size of $\Delta 2\theta = 0.015 \text{ °}$.

173 *2.3.4 X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)*

174 Surface chemical analysis was performed using a Nexsa G2 X-ray Photoelectron
175 Spectroscopy (XPS) system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). X-ray source: monochromatic Al

176 K α radiation. Specimens were analyzed under ultra-high vacuum conditions ($\leq 1 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar).
177 To enhance data reliability, measurements represent the average of two randomly selected
178 spots (200 μm in diameter). Survey scans were carried out at a pass energy of 100 eV and an
179 energy resolution of 1.0 eV, whilst high-resolution spectra were recorded at a pass energy of
180 20 eV and a resolution of 0.1 eV.

181 *2.3.5 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)*

182 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the AC specimens was performed using a TESCAN
183 VEGA3 microscope (TESCAN, Czech Republic) equipped with a secondary electron detector.
184 The microscope was operated at an acceleration voltage of 10 kV with a tungsten cathode as
185 the electron source. AC specimens were examined without additional coating and mounted on
186 the sample holder using carbon tape. SEM imaging of the paper precursor was carried out
187 using a Sigma VP microscope (Carl Zeiss Microscopy, Jena, Germany) operated at an
188 accelerating voltage of 0.7 kV with an in-lens detector. Prior to imaging, the paper precursor
189 was coated with an approximately 3 nm thick iridium layer using an ACE600 sputter coater
190 (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany). The paper cross-section was obtained by manually
191 sectioning the sample with a commercially available double edge razor blade (Wilkinson
192 Sword, Solingen, Germany) and subsequently sputter coated and imaged under the same
193 conditions as described prior.

194 *2.3.6 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)*

195 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to examine the prepared ACs. For
196 specimen preparation, a 300-mesh copper grid covered with a lacy carbon support film was
197 briefly immersed in a suspension of AC in acetone (1:1000, w/w). After evaporation of the
198 solvent, the grid was placed in the TEM holder. Imaging was performed using a JEM-2800
199 microscope (JEOL, Akishima, Tokyo, Japan) operated at an accelerating voltage of 200 keV,
200 and the images were acquired with an ORIUS SC200 CCD camera (GATAN, Pleasanton, CA,
201 USA).

202 2.3.7 Nitrogen adsorption experiments

203 Nitrogen adsorption measurements were performed at $-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (77 K) on a Quadrasorb SI
204 analyzer (Quantachrome Instruments). Before analysis, ~ 25 mg of each specimen was
205 degassed at $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h under dynamic vacuum using a FloVac degasser. SSA's were
206 calculated from the adsorption isotherms using the multi-point Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET)
207 method in the relative pressure range $p/p_0 = 0.05-0.3$. Micropore surface areas were obtained
208 with the t-plot method, while pore size distributions (PSD) were derived by applying quenched
209 solid density functional theory (QSDFT) for slit-shaped and cylindrical pore geometries.

210 2.3.7 SAXS

211 Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) data was collected using an SAXSpoint 2.0 instrument
212 (Anton Paar, Austria). Scattering data was collected using an Eiger 1M detector (Dectris,
213 Switzerland) positioned 110 and 572 mm from the sample, using a microfocused,
214 monochromatized X-ray source Cu $K\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm). The samples were held in the beam
215 between two pieces of Scotch Magic tape, and the resulting data was processed using the
216 DAWN software package, using standardized data correction procedures [73, 74]. The
217 corrected data were fit using McSAS3, based on Monte Carlo simulations, to obtain form-free
218 size distributions, using a spherical model [75].

219 3. Results and Discussion

220

221 Fig. 1. TGA and TGA-MS analysis of KOH-impregnated paper specimens: (a) total mass loss
 222 over the entire experiment with (c) the corresponding DTG curves; (b) normalized mass loss
 223 after the 1 h drying step during heating to 750 °C with (d) the corresponding DTG curves; (e)
 224 normalized mass loss of C35 with the corresponding CO₂ MS signal; (f) normalized mass loss

225 of C20 with the corresponding CO₂ MS signal; (g) normalized mass loss of C35 with the
226 corresponding H₂O MS signal; and (h) normalized mass loss of C20 with the corresponding
227 H₂O MS signal.

228

229 Fig. 2. Photographs of impregnated paper sheets before thermal treatment (a, c, e, g) and after
230 isothermal drying at 120 °C and subsequent heating to 250 °C (b, d, f, h).

231 Before heating, the specimens displayed distinct wetting characteristics. With the same KOH
232 mass but more water, C20 retains a visible external film of solution (Fig. 2, a), C25 and C30

233 take up most of the solution (Fig. 2 c, e), whereas in C35 the liquid is completely held within
 234 the fiber network (Fig. 2, g). The first and highest mass loss at ~92 °C (Fig. 1, a, c) corresponds
 235 to evaporation of free water. As C20 is wetted with the largest solution volume, it shows the
 236 greatest water loss, followed by C25 and C30, whereas C35 loses the least. To enable
 237 comparison of mass losses occurring during the cellulose-to-char transformation, the TGA and
 238 DTG curves were normalized at the point where heating resumed after the 60 min drying
 239 plateau (Fig. 1 b, d). MS data were recorded simultaneously with the TGA measurements for
 240 C20 and C35. The MS signals consistently appear at higher temperatures than the
 241 corresponding mass-loss events. This systematic shift arises from the transfer time of evolved
 242 gases traveling from the TGA furnace to the MS detector through the heated transfer line,
 243 which introduces a characteristic dwell time, and therefore temperature delay between gas
 244 evolution and its detection [76].

245 After the 120 °C/1 h drying step, the distribution of solid KOH differs. In C20, much of the KOH
 246 remains on the sheet surface and has limited contact with the internal cellulose domains. With
 247 increasing uptake from C20 to C35, KOH is dispersed more evenly within the matrix. As
 248 potassium-catalyzed charring is ionic and contact-dependent [77], improved dispersion can
 249 enhance catalysis. Potassium lowers the activation barrier for cellulose degradation, causing
 250 the process to begin at significantly lower temperatures than in the absence of alkali [70, 78,
 251 79]. The main processes responsible for the mass loss associated with the DTG peak at 201
 252 °C are reactions of KOH with oxygen-containing functional groups, which can be described by
 253 the following simplified pathways [38]:

254 These reactions begin with acid-base neutralization between KOH and oxygen-containing
 255 surface groups, forming potassium carboxylates and phenolates, followed by their

256 deoxygenation, which releases gases such as H₂, CO₂, H₂O, and CH₄. During this process,
257 KOH is progressively transformed into K₂CO₃ and metallic K. The metallic potassium
258 intercalates into the developing carbon matrix, and its subsequent removal, either during the
259 isothermal high-temperature stage at 750 °C or during post-activation acid washing, leads to
260 the formation of a microporous network. At the same time, these reactions create surface
261 vacancies in the evolving char. OH⁻ originating from KOH rapidly occupies these vacancies,
262 introducing new O-containing groups on the biochar surface (C=O, -OH, C-O, O-C=O, -
263 COOH) [38]. As shown in the CO₂-MS curves of C35 and C20 (Fig. 1 e, f), the CO₂ released
264 via reaction (1) decreases with increasing temperature because KOH that is not directly
265 reacting with oxygen-containing cellulose groups captures the evolving CO₂ and forms
266 KHCO₃. The resulting carbonation to bicarbonate produces a slight mass increase, which is
267 visible in the TGA / DTG curves at 211 °C / 210 °C (Fig. 1 b, d). Since this mass gain event is
268 pronounced for C20 but nearly absent for C35, the extent of carbonation is higher in C20.

269 With further temperature increase, KHCO₃ decomposes to K₂CO₃ (2 KHCO₃ → K₂CO₃ + H₂O
270 + CO₂), while unreacted KOH can simultaneously undergo direct carbonation to K₂CO₃ (2 KOH
271 + CO₂ → K₂CO₃ + H₂O). Both reactions release H₂O, which appears in the H₂O-MS curves of
272 C20 and C35 as a deviation from the otherwise steadily decreasing signal (Fig. 1 g, h). The
273 onset of H₂O evolution occurs earlier for C20 (147 °C) than for C35 (179 °C), whereas both
274 signals decline again at ~225 °C, resulting in a broader water-release interval for C20. This
275 behavior indicates that carbonate formation, via bicarbonate decomposition and direct
276 carbonation of KOH to K₂CO₃ is more pronounced in C20. A small positive CO₂ peak at 233
277 °C is observed for C20 (Fig. 1 f) but is not discernible for C35 (Fig. 1 e), further supporting
278 bicarbonate decomposition in C20. These findings suggest that C20 initially contains a larger
279 fraction of KOH that is not in intimate contact with cellulose and is therefore more readily
280 available for bicarbonate formation and subsequent carbonation reactions.

281 The residual cellulosic framework undergoes condensation reactions of carbohydrate-derived
282 carbonyl fragments, forming an oxygen-rich, brown intermediate. Upon further heating, ring

283 formation (aromatization) transforms this intermediate into black char. After 250 °C (Fig. 2 b,
284 d, f, h), C35 appears completely black, while C30, C25, and especially C20 show progressively
285 less carbonization. The surface of C20 remains brown, and the degree of shrinkage increases
286 systematically from C20 to C35.

287 The subsequent DTG peak at 340 °C (onset ~260 °C) arises from several overlapping
288 processes, including the deoxygenation and decarboxylation of O-containing groups on the
289 char, formed during the initial reactions between precursor and KOH, as well as the
290 dehydration of residual KOH to K₂O. This transformation begins already at around 300 °C
291 when excess KOH is present [72, 80]. As the melting points of KOH and K₂O are 360 °C and
292 350 °C, respectively, heating above these temperatures produces a highly mobile ionic melt.
293 Evolving gases become partially trapped within this melt, promoting continuous
294 interconversion among K₂CO₃, K₂O, and KOH [29].

295 The H₂O and CO₂-MS signals provide additional insights into how the transformation of the
296 precursors proceeds. For C35, the H₂O signal intensity rises steadily after ~260 °C until the
297 end of carbonization, consistent with water release from deoxygenation and KOH dehydration.
298 In contrast, the H₂O signal of C20 remains nearly constant, indicating that a larger fraction of
299 the produced water is retained by potassium species in C20. This prolonged wet state slows
300 the char formation processes, indicating why C20 carbonizes more slowly than precursors
301 impregnated with lower KOH solution volumes. The rise in the CO₂-MS signal above 264 °C
302 for C35 and 309 °C for C20 is attributed mainly to the decarboxylation of oxygen-containing
303 functional groups on the evolving char. The second CO₂-evolution window (~ 390-500 °C)
304 coincides with the onset of chemical activation. In this region, potassium carboxylate species
305 formed by neutralization decompose [81], while molten potassium phases increasingly attack
306 more stable oxygen sites on the char, further contributing to the CO₂-MS signal. Above ~400
307 °C, excess KOH begins to directly attack the carbon framework [38]. In addition to CO₂
308 formation, these redox reactions generate H₂, which likely contributes to the DTG peaks
309 observed between 435 and 448 °C.

310 Once KOH is fully consumed and converted to K_2CO_3 , CO_2 is no longer effectively captured
 311 and is instead released, giving rise to the DTG peak near 549 °C and the corresponding CO_2 -
 312 MS maxima at 564 °C (C35) and 567 °C (C20). Beyond this point, the mass stabilizes, marking
 313 the end of KOH-driven chemical activation. Subsequent physical activation is then dominated
 314 by the Boudouard reaction ($CO_2 + C \rightarrow 2 CO$). This process consumes the released CO_2 ,
 315 which is consistent with the decline in the CO_2 -MS signal. Unlike C35, the CO_2 -MS signal of
 316 C20 increases again sharply and forms a second peak around 720 °C. This high-temperature
 317 CO_2 release is attributed to the decomposition of K_2CO_3 to K_2O , with the liberated CO_2
 318 promoting a second stage of physical activation in C20. This enhanced physical activation in
 319 C20 likely results in more extensive pore widening and pore coalescence, as well as additional
 320 micropore formation.

321
 322 Fig. 3. ATR-FTIR spectra of the impregnated paper sheets after isothermal drying at 120 °C
 323 and subsequent heating to 250 °C.

324 ATR-FTIR spectra of the KOH-impregnated sheets after treatment at 250 °C (Fig. 3) differ
 325 fundamentally from those of untreated cellulose. The characteristic cellulose fingerprint bands
 326 previously identified for this precursor paper in our earlier work [2] (1426, 1364, 1333, 1314,
 327 1200, 1159 cm^{-1}), as well as the 1103-1000 cm^{-1} region and the β -glycosidic band at 896 cm^{-1} ,

328 are not observed here, indicating that the probed surface is no longer dominated by intact
329 cellulose. However, carbohydrate-derived intermediates formed during the initial charring of
330 cellulose (polyfuranic/humin-like structures) likely contribute to the remaining broad absorption
331 envelope with a local maximum at $\sim 1349\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [82].

332 Instead, the spectra are dominated by a set of bands consistent with the formation of an
333 incipient carbonaceous structure together with a substantial contribution from inorganic
334 carbonate species. The bands at 1593 and 1558 cm^{-1} lie in a region assigned to aromatic C=C
335 skeletal stretching in thermally converted lignocellulosic materials, indicating progressive
336 aromatization during treatment [83, 84]. The presence of carbonate is evidenced by the band
337 at 1440 cm^{-1} , attributed to the ν_3 asymmetric C–O stretching of CO_3^{2-} , together with the band
338 at 1059 cm^{-1} , which falls within the range reported for the ν_1 symmetric C–O stretching of
339 carbonate species [85]. The bands at 879 and 843 cm^{-1} are assigned to the ν_2 out-of-plane
340 bending mode of carbonate. The additional component at 843 cm^{-1} is attributed to ν_2 splitting
341 or a frequency shift arising from carbonate species in non-equivalent local environments, as
342 reported for structurally heterogeneous or amorphous carbonate phases [86-88]. Its resolution
343 in C35 therefore reflects local heterogeneity, which may stem from differences in hydration
344 state (e.g., coexistence of less hydrated and more strongly hydrated carbonate species), but
345 could also be related to variations in coordination, ion pairing, or structural disorder. The bands
346 observed at 700 and 668 cm^{-1} are attributed to the ν_4 in-plane bending mode of carbonate [86,
347 89]. In addition, the shoulder around 1630 cm^{-1} can be attributed to adsorbed water [90].

348 Peak resolution increases from C20 to C35, even though C35 is visually more carbonized.
349 ATR-FTIR probes only the first micron-scale region in close contact with the crystal, and in wet
350 media the measured spectrum is dominated by an interfacial water film with only a weak
351 contribution from the solid. Accordingly, the wetter C20 exhibits stronger water-film masking,
352 and a higher fraction of potassium species remain dissolved rather than precipitated at the
353 surface, both of which diminish apparent band intensities and blur fine spectral features. In
354 contrast, the more carbonized specimens (C30 and C35) present a drier, more rigid surface

355 with surface-precipitated carbonate species, resulting in sharper and more intense carbonate-
 356 and aromatic-related bands.

357

358 Fig. 4. (a) Stacked XRD patterns of KOH-impregnated paper sheets after drying (120 °C, 1 h)
 359 and subsequent heating to 250 °C (C20-C35_250 °C), compared with untreated paper and
 360 simulated reference patterns of potassium carbonates ($K_2CO_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ and K_2CO_3) and

361 graphite (all simulated from CIF files [91-93]). (b) Enlarged view of the highlighted 2θ region;
362 corresponding 2θ positions are listed in Table S1.

363 The XRD diffractograms of the KOH-treated, thermally converted sheets (Fig. 4) deviate
364 strongly from that of the precursor paper, indicating that the native cellulose structure is largely
365 lost already at 250 °C. This is consistent with the pronounced optical changes observed after
366 thermal treatment (Fig. 2).

367 C20-C35_250°C exhibit numerous reflections across $2\theta \sim 5\text{-}25^\circ$ (Fig. 4 a), with the expanded
368 view highlighting a particularly peak-rich region between ~ 12 and 21° (Fig. 4 b). These
369 reflections overlap with potassium carbonate reference patterns ($\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and K_2CO_3).
370 This assignment agrees with the ATR-FTIR results (Fig. 3), where carbonate vibrational bands
371 dominate the spectra. Within the series, C20-C30_250°C display similar peak sets with only
372 minor peak position offsets, suggesting small variations in carbonate hydration state and/or
373 crystallinity. In contrast, C35 lacks several reflections present in C20-C30_250°C (e.g., peaks
374 3, 5, 6, 9, 16, and 17 in Fig. 4 b; exact 2θ positions are listed in Table S1), indicating either a
375 modified salt mixture or altered phase proportions. Since these salts are hygroscopic,
376 differences in ambient exposure and sample handling may have contributed to the apparent
377 disappearance of reflections in C35_250°C.

378 No distinct graphite-related reflections are observed in C20-C35_250°C. This is expected
379 because treatment at 250 °C does not produce considerable graphitic order; any carbon
380 formed at this stage is largely amorphous and would contribute only a broad, low-intensity
381 background feature rather than sharp peaks.

382

383 Fig. 5. (a) Carbon yield relative to precursor mass, (b) Fraction of K-salts calculated from the
 384 masses of washed and unwashed AC, and images of unwashed ACs produced with 35 w.%
 385 (c) and 20 w.% (d) KOH solution.

386 The carbon yield decreases with increasing KOH solution volume used for precursor
 387 impregnation (Fig. 5, a), with the yield of C35 being nearly an order of magnitude higher than
 388 that of C20. The generally low yields (<10%) are typical for the one-step KOH activation
 389 process, since the yield is calculated relative to the mass of the original precursor rather than
 390 a pre-carbonized intermediate, and because cellulosic precursors undergo extensive chemical
 391 etching due to their highly reactive functional groups.

392 Alkaline hydrolysis, during which anhydroglucose units are removed from the cellulose
 393 backbone and released as soluble degradation products, proceeds for a longer time in
 394 specimens impregnated with higher KOH solution volumes. These specimens remain wet for
 395 a longer period of time, delaying the onset of carbonization to higher temperatures (Fig. 2
 396 b,d,f,h). Consequently, a larger fraction of the original cellulose is converted into non-
 397 carbonizing volatile products in C20. However, with the reduction of the KOH solution volume,

398 the duration of alkaline degradation decreases and aromatization begins earlier, preserving a
399 larger fraction of the cellulose backbone that subsequently forms the carbon matrix. This
400 explains the increase in carbon yield from C20 to C35. In addition, the CO₂-MS signal indicates
401 that C20 undergoes an additional high-temperature physical activation step at approximately
402 720 °C. During this process, CO₂ reacts with carbon, which further reduces the carbon yield.

403 The K-salt residues on the unwashed ACs (Fig. 5 b) originate from reactions of KOH with CO₂
404 and H₂O during thermal treatment. A decreasing trend in K-salt content is observed with
405 decreasing KOH solution volume. However, the difference in salt mass between C20 and C35
406 is only about 5%, which is unexpected considering the pronounced visual differences in the
407 unwashed ACs (Fig. 5 c,d). While C35 appears uniformly black with a foam-like texture, C20
408 exhibits a black carbon core surrounded by a white crust of K-salts. This contrast indicates that
409 the applied KOH solution volume controls whether potassium salts form predominantly as
410 external crusts or remain more uniformly distributed within the carbon matrix after activation.

411 In C35, the entire solution volume is absorbed into the precursor paper, resulting in K₂CO₃
412 formation predominantly within the bulk. In contrast, in C20 the solution volume exceeds the
413 absorption capacity of the paper. A substantial fraction of KOH therefore does not interact with
414 internal cellulose domains and instead converts externally to K₂CO₃, producing the
415 pronounced salt crust (Fig. 5 d).

AC composition after a single washing step with 1M HCl:

416

417 Fig. 6. (a, b) Surface atomic composition obtained by XPS for AC samples (C20-C35) after
 418 one HCl wash. (c-f) High-resolution C 1s spectra and corresponding peak fitting showing the
 419 contributions of different carbon functional groups for C20, C25, C30, and C35.

AC composition after a second washing step with 1M HCl:

420

421 Fig. 7. (a, b) Surface atomic composition obtained by XPS of C30 and C35 after a second HCl
 422 wash. (c, d) High-resolution C 1s spectra and corresponding peak fitting showing the
 423 contributions of different carbon functional groups for the rewashed C30 and C35.

424 XPS probes the near-surface elemental composition and is therefore highly sensitive to trace
 425 residues and surface contamination. For the present ACs (Fig. 6 & 7, a, b), C represents the
 426 carbon matrix. O arises from oxygen-containing surface functionalities generated during KOH
 427 activation and from oxygen containing inorganic residues such as K_2CO_3 . Residual K is
 428 attributed to activator-derived potassium species that are not fully removed by a single washing
 429 step, including K-O surface complexes and potassium salts (e.g., carbonates). Trace S is
 430 consistent with the acid sulfite origin of the cellulose fibers, whereas Si and Al likely reflect
 431 minor ash/mineral impurities (e.g., aluminosilicates). Fluorine is not expected to originate from
 432 either the cellulose precursor or the activation chemistry. Its presence therefore suggests

433 contamination from an external fluorine-containing source introduced during processing,
434 potentially from the sealing rings of the tube furnace. N may originate from trace precursor
435 residues and/or adsorption.

436 The changes induced by the second washing step in the AC surface composition (Fig. 7, a &
437 b) indicate that a substantial fraction of the XPS oxygen signal originates from oxygen-
438 containing potassium residues. After the second wash, the surface oxygen content decreases
439 strongly (C30_1×HCl: 30.1 → C30_2×HCl: 10.6 at.% ; C35_1×HCl: 23.1 → C35_2×HCl: 12.3
440 at.%). Potassium and contaminations such as Si, Al, and F are no longer detected. This
441 behavior is consistent with the dissolution of residual K-salts and their associated oxygen
442 species and is further supported by the disappearance of K-related contributions in the high-
443 resolution spectra (Fig. 7, c & d). As a result, the surface compositions of C30_2×HCl and
444 C35_2×HCl converge to very similar values (O ~ 11-12 at.%, S ~ 0.3-0.4 at.%, N ~ 0.5 at.%).
445 These observations indicate that the elevated oxygen contents measured after the first wash
446 were largely due to removable oxygen-containing K residues. With K being removed, the C 1s
447 envelope is dominated by the carbon scaffold (C-C/C=C), together with a smaller but distinct
448 contribution from covalently bound oxygen functional groups, mainly C–OH/C–O with minor
449 C=O and O–C=O components (Fig. 7, c & d). Such oxygen-containing groups are
450 advantageous when the material is used as an electrode in energy-storage devices employing
451 aqueous electrolytes (e.g. aqueous supercapacitors systems), because they improve
452 electrolyte wetting of the porous network and facilitate ion access to internal surface sites [94].

453 The AC atomic composition after the first and second wash (Fig. 6 & Fig. 7, a, b) are consistent
454 with the visually observed differences in potassium-salt distribution in the unwashed
455 specimens (Fig. 5, c & d). For C20, photographs show a superficial salt crust that is readily
456 dissolved during the first washing step. Accordingly, K drops below the XPS detection limit and
457 the associated oxygen signal is strongly reduced. In contrast, for C35 the photographs indicate
458 that potassium compounds are more embedded within the carbon structure. This lower
459 accessibility is reflected in the XPS results, where K remains detectable after the first wash

460 and is only removed after the second washing step. These results indicate that the
461 effectiveness of washing is governed less by the total amount of residual potassium and more
462 by its spatial distribution, which is directly dependent on the KOH solution volume used during
463 impregnation of the AC precursors.

464

465 Fig. 8. Microscopy images showing SEM micrographs of the precursor paper surface (a) and
 466 cross-section (b) at 200x magnification, and of the ACs derived from it (c-f) at 3000x

467 magnification. TEM images of the ACs produced using the lowest KOH solution volume (35
468 w.%) are shown in (g) and (h).

469 Electron microscopy of the washed ACs demonstrates that using the same precursor paper
470 (P0) (Fig. 8 a, b) but varying the KOH solution volume leads to pronounced differences in the
471 macropore architecture (Fig. 8 c-f). Since the paper fibers and the bulk paper structure can
472 absorb only a finite volume of solution, variations in the total solution volume result in different
473 KOH distributions within the precursor. This is reflected in the distinct spatial distribution of K-
474 salt deposits observed in the unwashed ACs (Fig. 5 c,d). Consequently, the activation
475 proceeds via different pathways, as supported by TGA-MS data and visual inspection of the
476 specimens after heating to 250°C (Fig. 2 b, d, f, h).

477 SEM analysis reveals clear differences in macroporous morphology across the AC series (Fig.
478 8 c-f). Among all specimens, C20 exhibits the largest macropores, whereas the macropore
479 sizes of C25, C30, and C35 are comparatively similar. In contrast, a systematic trend is
480 observed in the pore wall thickness, which decreases progressively from C20 to C35. These
481 morphological differences can be explained by the underlying activation mechanisms. In C35,
482 the wet alkaline hydrolysis stage terminates at lower temperatures than in C20, allowing a
483 larger fraction of degraded cellulose fragments to be converted into solid carbon rather than
484 lost as volatile species. These fragments are incorporated into the evolving carbon scaffold,
485 promoting a higher structural density and stability. As a result, a finer macroporous structure
486 with thinner pore walls is formed. Moreover, an additional high-temperature physical activation
487 step at 720 °C in C20 (Fig. 1, f) contributes not only to further micropore formation but also to
488 pore widening, producing a coarser macroporous morphology. During this process, the most
489 exposed and fine structural features are removed, leaving a framework dominated by fewer,
490 thicker pore walls. The intermediate specimens C25 and C30 exhibit macropore sizes similar
491 to C35 but slightly thicker pore walls, suggesting that physical activation is present but less
492 pronounced than in C20. This indicates a gradual transition in activation behavior across the
493 series, with decreasing contribution from physical activation from C20 to C35.

494 High-resolution TEM of C35 (Fig. 8 g, h) further reveals that, in addition to macropores, a
 495 substantial degree of microporosity is present. The micropores predominantly appear as slit-
 496 shaped voids formed between stacked graphene layers. The carbon framework of C35
 497 appears partially ordered and turbostratic, with short, curved, and misoriented lattice fringes
 498 that locally form bent stacked lamellae. In some regions, the fringes show concentric or onion-
 499 like curvature. These features suggest the presence of small graphitic microdomains
 500 (graphene-like crystallites) rather than long-range ordered graphite, which is typical of
 501 chemically activated carbons.

502

503 Fig. 9. Differential pore volume distributions of the ACs derived from N₂ adsorption data: (a)
 504 PSD curves, (b) total SSA and (c) micropore-SSA (pores < 2 nm) calculated from N₂ adsorption
 505 measurements.

506 Nitrogen adsorption measurements cannot probe ultra-micropores (≤ 0.7 nm) due to the
 507 molecular size of N₂ [2]. Therefore, the obtained PSD and SSA only reflect pores accessible

508 to N₂ and do not represent the full porosity. However, N₂ adsorption remains an important
509 complementary technique, as it provides quantitative information on the SSA and pore volume
510 of the micro- and mesopores that are accessible to gas molecules. The PSD (Fig. 9, a) shows
511 that C20 exhibits the highest pore volume in the 1.2-1.3 nm range as well as in the mesopore
512 region (2-5 nm). In contrast, C35 displays the lowest pore volume in these pore size ranges,
513 while C25 and C30 show similar intermediate values, lying between C20 and C35.

514 Considering that pore development in C20 was more strongly driven by physical activation due
515 to the early conversion of a large fraction of KOH into potassium salts compared with
516 specimens impregnated with lower KOH solution volume, its higher porosity in the N₂-
517 accessible range, particularly in the mesoporous region, is reasonable. CO₂-MS data further
518 support this interpretation, revealing CO₂ release from the decomposition of K₂CO₃ at
519 approximately 720 °C in C20. This CO₂ evolution promotes additional pore growth, leading to
520 increased mesopore volume and, on a larger scale, the formation of large macropores, as
521 confirmed by SEM (Fig. 9, c).

522 C20 exhibits the highest pore volume within the N₂-accessible pore size range, mainly due to
523 its pronounced contribution of mesopores (2-5 nm), which results in the highest SSA (1455
524 m²/g). The SSA decreases toward C35, reaching 1276 m²/g. In contrast, the relative micropore
525 contribution to the SSA (pores <2 nm) increases from 65% for C20 to 83% for C35, while
526 remaining nearly constant for C25 and C30 (76% and 75%, respectively).

527

528 Fig. 10. PSD's of the ACs determined by SAXS: (a) C20, (b) C25, (c) C30 and (d) C35.

529 SAXS analysis (Fig. 10) indicates a decrease in the pore volume fraction from C20 to C35,
 530 which is consistent with enhanced physical activation arising from the higher K_2CO_3 presence
 531 associated with the use of larger KOH solution volumes during impregnation. This trend is in
 532 good agreement with the N_2 adsorption-derived SSA (Fig.9 b), which likewise decreases from
 533 C20 to C35.

534 Concurrently, a shift toward smaller pore sizes is observed. The mean pore diameter
 535 decreases from 1.52 nm (C20) to 1.26 nm (C35), while all specimens remain dominated by
 536 pores in the ~1-2 nm size range, indicating that the primary microporous structure is preserved
 537 across the series. The dominant pore-size population of the N_2 -derived PSDs is at ~0.9 nm
 538 (Figure 9 a), which does not appear to align with the SAXS derived mean diameters. This may
 539 indicate N_2 -inaccessible porosity in that size range, e.g., blocked pores not open to the surface
 540 or bottleneck pores with entrances too narrow for N_2 to access. Beyond this modest shift in the
 541 mean pore diameter, clear differences emerge in the contribution of larger pores. In particular,
 542 C20 exhibits the highest pore volume fraction at diameters above the mean, indicating an

543 enhanced contribution from pores in the upper micropore to small-mesopore size regime. This
544 behavior is consistent with the most pronounced pore widening/merging, attributable to etching
545 by CO_2 released during K_2CO_3 decomposition (Fig 1, f). In contrast, the pore volume
546 associated with these larger diameters is lower for C25 and C30, and smallest for C35.

547 C25 and C30 display similar pore size distributions, both in terms of the main peak position
548 and the overall PSD shape. Their mean pore diameters differ only slightly (1.42 nm for C30
549 and 1.50 nm for C25), indicating that increasing the KOH solution volume from C30 to C25
550 does not significantly alter the dominant pore population. This observation is further supported
551 by the N_2 adsorption-derived PSDs and $\text{SSA}_{\text{micro}}/\text{SSA}$ trends, which are also almost identical
552 for C25 and C30. Together, these results point to the presence of a plateau in the relationship
553 between KOH solution volume and AC pore size, with substantial additional pore enlargement
554 occurring only at the highest solution volume (C20).

555 **4. Conclusion**

556 Overall, the results demonstrate that the amount of water used to dissolve a constant KOH
557 mass, and thus the applied KOH solution volume, acts as a decisive parameter in the one-step
558 conversion of cellulose-based precursors into AC. Changing the solution volume modifies the
559 starting conditions for the pyrolysis, which in turn shifts the dominant activation pathway and
560 ultimately determines carbon yield and pore structure. At high KOH solution volume (C20), the
561 amount of solution exceeds the absorption capacity of the paper precursor. As a result, a
562 substantial fraction of KOH remains poorly integrated with the cellulose matrix, favoring its
563 conversion into K_2CO_3 rather than direct participation in KOH-cellulose reactions. In contrast,
564 at lower KOH solution volume (C35), the entire solution is readily absorbed by the paper,
565 ensuring intimate contact between KOH and cellulose throughout the precursor. Under these
566 conditions, the formation of K_2CO_3 is reduced, and the activation mechanism is therefore
567 dominated by chemical activation, with only a minor contribution from subsequent physical
568 activation.

569 In C20, the excess KOH preferentially reacts with water and CO₂ released during cellulose
570 degradation, leading to extensive KHCO₃ and K₂CO₃ formation. The associated retention of
571 water within these salts alters the local reaction environment and delays effective
572 carbonization. As a result, the prolonged wet, highly alkaline conditions promote alkaline
573 hydrolysis of cellulose into volatile, non-carbonizing fragments, thereby reducing the carbon
574 yield. With decreasing KOH solution volume from C20 to C35, the extent of alkaline hydrolysis
575 is reduced, leading to earlier aromatization and char formation. Besides the apparent color
576 change (Fig. 2), ATR-FTIR confirms that char formation already occurs at 250 °C, with the
577 cellulose structure being largely degraded. Additionally, ATR-FTIR and XRD reveal that the
578 surface chemistry is dominated by potassium carbonate phases (K₂CO₃·1.5H₂O and K₂CO₃).

579 These differences in the activation pathway also govern pore development. In C35, early
580 charring combined with reduced volatile loss results in a dense, finely developed macroporous
581 structure with thin pore walls. In contrast, stronger physical activation in C20 leads to the loss
582 of fine structural features, producing a coarser morphology with thicker pore walls. The extra
583 release of CO₂ in C20 further promotes micropore formation and micropore merging,
584 increasing the total pore volume and, in particular, enhancing mesoporosity. As the strength
585 of this physical activation mechanism decreases with decreasing KOH solution volume, both
586 the total pore volume and the mesoporous contribution systematically decrease from C20 to
587 C35. However, this decrease is not linear with decreasing solution volume, as the
588 microstructural properties of the intermediate specimens C25 and C30 are very similar. This
589 plateau in the relationship between KOH solution volume and AC pore size is reflected in both
590 N₂ adsorption and SAXS results, indicating that substantial additional pore enlargement occurs
591 only once the precursor's absorption capacity is significantly exceeded.

592 Beyond the specific system studied here, these findings demonstrate that activator distribution
593 plays a central role in the thermal transformation of cellulose. They show that not only the
594 activator-to-precursor mass ratio, but also the extent to which the activator is absorbed into the
595 bulk of the precursor versus remaining externally located, governs reaction pathways, pore

596 evolution, and carbon yield. Consequently, a carefully designed impregnation strategy is
597 required to achieve reproducible and application-specific AC properties and represents a key
598 parameter for the scale-up of one-step KOH activation processes for biomass.

599 **CRedit authorship contribution statement:**

600 Alexa Scheer: Conceptualization, Production of precursor and ACs, Methodology - SEM, FT-
601 IR, TGA, Writing - Original Draft

602 Hoang Bao Tran Nguyen: Conceptualization, Methodology - N₂ Adsorption, XRD, Writing -
603 Review & Editing

604 Johanna Fischer: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing

605 Glen J Smales: Methodology - SAXS, Writing - Review & Editing

606 Julian Selinger: Methodology - SEM, TEM, Writing - Review & Editing

607 Ahmad Alem: Methodology - XPS, Writing - Review & Editing

608 Christine Bandl: Methodology - XPS, Writing - Review & Editing

609 Steffen Fischer: Conceptualization, Funding, Writing - Review & Editing

610 Daria Mikhailova: Conceptualization, Funding, Writing - Review & Editing

611 Stefan Spirk: Conceptualization, Funding, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision

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613 The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be
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